

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

GLORIA GERALDINE S. VICTORIA

Assistant School Principal II / MAED Student

DepEd Laguna - Liliw Senior High School / Greenville College

gloriageraldine.victoria@deped.gov.ph

“ENHANCE-READING EMPOWERMENT ASSERTING CONNECTION AT HOMEROOM (E-REACH): A READING INTERVENTION FOR GRADE 12 STRUGGLING LEARNERS”

Reading plays an important role in the development and well-being of the students. It boosts communication skills, supports mental health, and improves the ability to learn and adapt to new information. Additionally, reading is crucial for success in school and essential to every aspect of life. Comprehending what we read is one of the most complex cognitive activities that the humans undertake, making it challenging to teach and measure. Enhancing reading comprehension among adolescents will require a united effort from educators, policymakers and teachers to prioritize long-term solutions over a short-term achievement that only address basic comprehension levels. In line with the school's ongoing efforts to strengthen literacy skills among Senior High School students and align with the Department of Education's agenda for improving comprehension skills at Liliw Senior High School, Project E-REACH (Enhance-Reading Empowerment Asserting Connection at Homeroom) was developed as a strategic intervention program to address the literacy challenges faced by ten (10) Grade 12 students identified as struggling readers and writers. These ten students have shown difficulties in analyzing texts, they also possess limited vocabulary, and exhibit lower reading comprehension and written expression skills which are essential for the improvement of academic performance and lifelong learning. The program was designed to meet the urgent need for targeted, responsive, and innovative support to improve their literacy skills. Through differentiated instruction, guided reading sessions, contextualized and localized activities, Project E-REACH aims to bridge learning gaps among identified struggling learners, build their confidence, and foster a positive attitude toward reading and writing. Additionally, it seeks to prepare learners for the literacy demands necessary for completing senior high school as well as future employment or further education. By conducting intensive interventions to address the individual needs of the struggling learners, Project E-REACH aspires to empower them to realize their full academic potential and become more competent and confident communicators. The implementation of this project started in August 2024 and ended in March 2025 through enhancement classes that utilized computer tablets and other electronic devices under the guidance of English teachers and student leaders acting as peer tutors. Establish connections between the teacher and peer students to develop and enhance the reading skills of the struggling learners.

The program successfully enhanced literacy and comprehension skills, with 9 out of 10 or 90% of students from a low literate level to literate level. This underscores the project's effectiveness in using technology-assisted instruction to close learning gaps and improve student performance in English and related subjects. Moreover, sustaining the projects and provide additional support ensuring that they acquire the essential literacy and comprehension skills necessary for academic success.